

Harnessing Digital Potential: A TAMBAGE Framework for Integrating E-Learning in Teaching TLE

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ABSTRACT

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is one of the core subjects in the Philippines education curriculum that designed to equip students with technical and practical skills required for work and livelihood. Despite the potential of e-learning in enhancing TLE instruction, its integration in public schools, particularly in the Division of Agusan del Sur, remains challenging due to limited access to digital resources due to their socio-economic conditions, leading the research to explore the attitudes of educators towards e-learning and evaluating the effectiveness of various e-learning tools and platforms. The study employed quantitative research design and the primary tool for data collection is a modified questionnaire in the fields of current landscape, attitude, challenges, effectiveness and best practices of TLE teachers in integrating E-learning. The study involved two districts with 376 respondents coming from students and 69 from teachers. The results revealed that both teachers and students express satisfaction with the current landscape of TLE teaching and methodologies. Teachers and students demonstrate a strong satisfaction with the perceived attitude of TLE educators in integrating e-learning

Keywords: *E-learning, Teacher engagement, Student engagement, Learning outcomes, Digital potential, Effectiveness, Attitude, Challenges, Framework, TLE*

INTRODUCTION

Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) is one of the core subjects in the Philippines education curriculum that designed to equip students with technical and practical skills required for work and livelihood. In this era of digital transformation, the public schools have dramatically evolved from traditional teaching to the integration of e-learning in teaching TLE. While e-learning has potential to improve teaching skills and an increase student's learning capabilities, the extent of its actual significant challenge in the level of digital literacy among teachers and students which hinder the effective implementation of e-learning.

Several research conducted in the implementation of effective teaching approaches in the use e-learning. The study of Curan (2023) revealed that students are more interested in TLE subjects when teacher's possess adequate material, implying that e-learning integration would results in student's active learning (Rodriguez & Habla, 2023). On the other hand, Ashish and Anitha (2018) suggested that utilization of ICT has the potential to enhance personalized instruction and provide improved monitoring of students' progress. Meanwhile, Encarnacion et al. (2021) emphasized that e-learning technologies in distance learning can democratize education by breaking traditional classroom barriers, while Radtke (2023) stressed the importance of effective instructors, well-designed courses, and timely feedback for successful e-learning experiences.

Despite the potential of e-learning in enhancing TLE instruction, its integration in public schools, particularly in the Division of Agusan del Sur, remains challenging due to limited access to digital resources especially to the students who lacked personal devices due to their socio-economic conditions. Studies have highlighted the benefits of e-learning, yet there is a lack of empirical data on its effectiveness in TLE, especially in rural settings where internet connectivity and technological infrastructure are insufficient. This study seeks to bridge these gaps by examining the current landscape of e-learning integration in TLE and identifying strategies to optimize its implementation

Thus, the researcher finds it valuable conduct this study to address challenges in TLE by utilizing digital tools effective strategies for integrating e-learning in TLE education. Ensuring equitable access to digital learning aligns with the Department of Education's (DepEd) goal of embracing 21st-century teaching and delivering quality education under the MATATAG curriculum.

Research Questions

The study aimed to assess how perceived attitude of TLE educators, and the challenges and barriers faced by TLE educators relates in integrating e-learning in TLE teaching among Trento Cluster and San Francisco Cluster of the Division of Agusan del Sur. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What is the current landscape of TLE teaching and methodologies of integrating of E-learning in terms of:
 - a. Teaching Approaches in TLE
 - b. Utilization of E-Learning Tools
 - c. Integration of E-Learning in TLE

- d. Teacher Preparedness and Training
 - e. Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes
2. What is the perceived attitude of TLE educators towards integrating E-learning into their teaching practices?
 3. What is the extent of effectiveness of the E-learning tools and platforms in enhancing students' engagement and learning outcomes in TLE subject?
 4. Is there a significant relationship between the current landscape of TLE teaching and methodologies and the extent of effectiveness of the E-learning tools and platforms in enhancing students' engagement and learning outcomes in TLE subject?
 5. What are the best practices of TLE teachers in integrating E-learning into TLE curriculum?
 6. What are the challenges and barriers faced by TLE educators in integrating e-learning in TLE teaching?
 7. Is there a significant relationship between perceived attitude of TLE educators and the challenges and barriers faced by TLE educators in integrating e-learning in TLE teaching?
 8. What educational framework can be developed based on the findings of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This research employed a descriptive-correlational research design will identify the relationship between the perceived attitudes of TLE educators toward integrating e-learning into their teaching practices and the extent of effectiveness of e-learning tools current landscape of TLE teaching and methodologies and the extent of effectiveness of e-learning tools, and platforms in enhancing students' engagement and learning outcomes in TLE subjects. Data were collected from Trento Cluster and San Francisco Cluster of the Division of Agusan del Sur comprising 376 respondents coming from students and 69 from teachers. The selection process involved random sampling to target individuals with specific expertise in TLE and e-learning integration.

The study utilized a researcher-designed questionnaire as the primary data collection tool, creating a comprehensive survey to understand various aspects of e-learning integration in TLE. The questionnaire underwent validation by experts, followed by a pilot test to refine the instrument before distribution. Statistical tools such as mean, and Pearson R correlation were utilized to analyze the data.

RESULTS

Table 1. Current Landscape of TLE Teaching and Methodologies

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Grand Mean	Over-all Adjective Rating
	Mean	Adjective Rating	Mean	Adjective Rating		
Teaching Approaches	4.60	SA	3.91	A	4.23	SA
Utilization of E-learning	4.32	SA	3.80	A	4.06	A
Integration of E-learning	4.32	SA	3.84	A	4.08	A
Teacher-Preparedness	4.04	A	3.79	A	3.91	A
Student Engagement	4.28	SA	3.89	A	4.09	A
Over-all Mean	4.30	SA	3.84	A	4.07	A

Table 2. Perceived Attitude of TLE Educators in Integrating E-learning

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Grand Mean	Over-all Adjective Rating
	Mean	Adjective Rating	Mean	Adjective Rating		
I am open to integrating E-learning into my TLE teaching practices.	4.52	SA	3.85	A	4.19	A
I believe integrating E-learning enhances student learning experiences.	4.65	SA	3.88	A	4.27	SA
I am willing to explore new E-learning tools and platforms.	4.62	SA	3.86	A	4.24	SA
I actively seek out opportunities to improve my E-learning integration skills.	4.61	SA	3.98	A	4.30	SA
I have a positive attitude toward incorporating technology into my teaching.	4.57	SA	3.93	A	4.25	SA
Over-all Mean	4.60	SA	3.90	A	4.25	SA

Table 3. Extent of Effectiveness of E-learning Tools

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Grand Mean	Over-all Adjective Rating
	Mean	Adjective Rating	Mean	Adjective Rating		
I have observed a positive impact on student engagement in TLE subjects using E-learning tools and platforms.	4.36	SA	3.85	A	4.11	A
I believe that E-learning tools and platforms effectively enhance students' learning outcomes in TLE subjects.	4.30	SA	3.92	A	4.11	A
I find that E-learning tools and platforms provide opportunities for personalized learning experiences in TLE subjects.	4.35	SA	3.88	A	4.12	A
I have noticed an improvement in students' understanding and retention of TLE concepts with the use of E-learning tools and platforms	4.33	SA	3.80	A	4.07	A
I believe that the use of E-learning tools and platforms contributes to a more interactive and engaging learning environment in TLE subjects.	4.45	SA	3.87	A	4.16	A
Over-all Mean	4.36	SA	3.86	A	4.11	A

Table 4. Significant Relationship between Current Landscape and Extent of Effectiveness

Variables Tested	Mean	Computed r	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Effectiveness of E-learning	Teaching Approaches	0.778	0.000	Reject H ₀	Highly Significant
	Utilization of E-learning	0.711	0.000	Reject H ₀	Highly Significant
	Integration of E-learning	0.708	0.000	Reject H ₀	Highly Significant
	Teacher-Preparedness	0.661	0.000	Reject H ₀	Highly Significant
	Student Engagement	0.805	0.000	Reject H ₀	Highly Significant

Table 5. Best Practices in Integrating E-learning

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Grand Mean	Over-all Adjective Rating
	Mean	Adjective Rating	Mean	Adjective Rating		
I actively seek out innovative ways to integrate E-learning into the TLE curriculum.	4.32	SA	3.92	A	4.12	A
I align E-learning activities objectives. with the TLE curriculum.	4.25	SA	3.86	A	4.06	A
I incorporate interactive and multimedia elements in E-learning materials for the TLE curriculum.	4.39	SA	3.93	A	4.16	A
I regularly evaluate and update E-learning resources and materials for the TLE curriculum	4.19	A	3.82	A	4.01	A
I provide ongoing support and guidance to students in utilizing E-learning tools for the TLE curriculum.	4.22	SA	3.88	A	4.05	A
Over-all Mean	4.27	SA	3.88	A	4.08	A

Table 6. Challenges and Barriers in Integrating E-learning

Indicators	Teachers		Students		Grand Mean	Over-all Adjective Rating
	Mean	Adjective Rating	Mean	Adjective Rating		
I face technical challenges when integrating E-learning in TLE teaching.	4.12	A	3.80	A	3.96	A
I encounter resistance from students when implementing E-learning in TLE teaching.	3.94	A	3.75	A	3.85	A
I struggle with limited access to necessary technology and resources for E-learning integration.	4.10	A	3.81	A	3.96	A
I find it challenging to adapt existing teaching methodologies to effectively incorporate E-learning.	4.00	A	3.82	A	s3.91	A
I do not have enough training and professional development opportunities for E-learning integration.	3.77	A	3.70	A	3.73	A
I feel curriculum adaptation for e-learning requires specialized training that is not readily available.	4.16	A	3.99	A	4.08	A
Over-all Mean	4.02	A	3.81	A	3.91	A

Table 7. Significant Relationship between Perceived Attitude and Challenges Faced in Integrating E-learning

Variables Tested	Computed r	p-value	Decision	Conclusion
Teacher's Perceived Attitude & Challenges Faced	0.543	0.000	Reject H _o	Highly Significant
Student's Perceived Attitude & Challenges Faced	0.550	0.000	Reject H _o	Highly Significant

DISCUSSION

The overall mean rating presented in table 1 suggests that teachers and students express strong satisfaction with the perceived attitude of TLE educators in integrating e-learning. The result aligns with findings by Bangcasan (2023), who observed that the quality of teaching practices in TLE directly impacts students' motivation and learning outcomes. Furthermore, Rajaram (2023) emphasized that aligning instructional strategies with new educational trends can sustain a good perception towards learners.

Table 2 presents the descriptive statistics results on the perceived attitude of TLE educators in integrating e-learning as rated by teachers and students. The overall mean rating suggests that teachers and students express strong satisfaction with the perceived attitude of TLE educators in integrating e-learning. A shared positive attitude between teachers and students regarding E-learning integration is often linked to improved learning outcomes and engagement. According to Asino and Pulay (2019) stressed that when teachers and students share a common understanding of technology's role in education, it promotes a collaborative learning environment that boosts motivation and enhances learning effectiveness.

The results in table 3 suggests that teachers and students' express satisfaction with the extent of effectiveness of e-learning tools. The general satisfaction aligns with the findings of Ware (2006) as cited by Hauver (2022), who observed that E-learning tools enhance technical instruction by providing flexible, learner-centered approaches. However, they emphasize continuous evaluation and improvement of these tools to ensure they meet the specific demands of technical education effectively.

Table 4 below presents the tests of a significant relationship between the current landscape and the extent of effectiveness. It can be gleaned from the table that all p-values are lesser than the level of significance at 0.01, this suggests there was a highly significant relationship between the current landscape and the extent of effectiveness. This implies that the utilization of e-learning tools will improve the teaching environment and can directly improve the educational experiences of learners. The results of the study aligned with the findings of Mishra and Koehler (2006) as cited by Scherer et al. (2019), that the TPCK framework emphasizes that utilizing technology integration may improve in teaching methodologies which contributes to enhance the functionality and perceived effectiveness of E-learning tools. Furthermore, research conducted by Ertmer et al.

(2012) as cited by Seufert et al. (2021) highlights that the success of E-learning tools depends on learning environment. Similarly, Al-Adwan et al. (2021) found that a well-structured teaching approach increases the benefits of E-learning tools, making them more effective in achieving learning objectives.

The overall mean rating in table 5 revealed that teachers and students' express satisfaction with the best practices in integrating e-learning. This suggests that both students and teachers recognize the effective strategies employed in utilizing E-learning for TLE. The research of Benbunan-Fich (2008) as cited by Yu et al. (2023) highlighted the best practices on the integration of E-learning, it was revealed that adopting multimedia integration is key to ensuring the success of blended and E-learning approaches. These practices not only improve student learning experiences but also enhance teachers' effectiveness in delivering technical subjects.

Results in table 6 suggests that teachers and students acknowledge the challenges and barriers in integrating E-learning. These challenges required teacher training, infrastructure development, and support for students' digital skills. The study of Bates (2018) recommends institutional support and collaboration between educators and policymakers to create an enabling environment for E-learning. Furthermore, Benbunan-Fich (2008) as cited by Yu et al. (2023), emphasizes the importance of fostering a culture of innovation and adaptability among educators to overcome barriers effectively.

It can be gleaned from the table 7 that all p-values are lesser than 0.01, indicating a highly significant relationship between perceived attitude and challenges faced in integrating e-learning both teachers and students. These findings suggest that as teachers' and students' positive attitudes towards E-learning increase, so does their awareness and acknowledgment of the challenges associated with its integration. The results align with findings conducted by Ertmer et al. (2012) as cited by Simanjuntak et al. (2022), that educators with positive attitudes toward technology are more willing to integrate it into their practices. Similarly, Teo (2011) as cited by Jang et al. (2021) highlights that a positive perception increases engagement will lead greater performance (Pizon & Ytoc, 2022)

Project TAMBAGE: Transforming Accessible Methods and Bridging Achievements Guided E-learning

Project TAMBAGE is based on the goal of the K–12 Program, often known as the new Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum, which is to create learners who are holistically developed. Teachers are crucial in developing successful and relevant e-learning environments to accomplish these aims. In addition to being proficient in TLE subject matter, they must also show that they are adept at incorporating technology, creating creative teaching methods, and encouraging student participation in a virtual learning environment. To guarantee that practical talents are successfully transferred into the online domain, they must also demonstrate a high degree of proficiency.

The **TAMBAGE Framework** serve as the foundation for enhancing positive attitudes and awareness toward e-learning and these are:

- **Transforming:** Making significant changes to improve teaching and learning practices.
- **Accessible:** Ensuring equal access to technology and learning resources.
- **Methods:** Strategies and techniques used for effective teaching and learning.
- **Bridging:** Connecting gaps between traditional and digital education.
- **Achievements:** Measurable successes in teaching and learning outcomes.
- **Guided:** Providing support and direction for teachers and students.
- **E-Learning:** Using digital tools and platforms for education delivery.

The support from the school head, co-teachers, and stakeholders to ensure an enabling and supportive environment is also necessary.

School heads play crucial role in promoting a supportive learning environment, which is important for the successful implementation of e-learning in TLE topics. As stated in **DepEd Order No. 24, s. 2020**, school administrators will help their teachers to by offering technical support based on observations in the classroom and professional learning and development (L&D) requirements. Under the developed **TAMBAGE** framework this will help to reach the realization of the guidelines which is to assess teachers and even students successfully incorporating e-learning into TLE disciplines.

This is also achieved by the help of school administrators utilizing collaborations with e-learning specialists and stakeholders who may lead capacity-building workshops.

Furthermore, school heads must carefully assigned teaching loads and other tasks to ensure that teachers have sufficient time to prepare effective e-learning lessons. This may achieved by implementing proper workload to prevents burnout and supports teachers in enhancing the quality of e-learning delivery in TLE subject.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

The study concludes that both teachers and students express a high level of satisfaction with the current landscape of TLE teaching methodologies, indicating that existing teaching approaches effectively engage learners. However, teacher preparedness remains an area that requires improvement to further enhance instructional effectiveness.

Teachers and students demonstrate a positive attitude toward integrating e-learning into TLE, emphasizing its potential to improve student learning experiences. Their openness to utilizing e-learning suggests a willingness to adopt innovative teaching strategies, which could lead to better engagement and learning outcomes.

The effectiveness of e-learning tools in TLE is well-recognized by both teachers and students, highlighting the role of digital platforms in fostering interactive and engaging learning environments. These tools significantly contribute to enhancing student understanding and participation in TLE subjects.

A significant relationship exists between the current educational landscape and the effectiveness of e-learning integration. This conclude that the current educational landscape improves the more its effective in the integration of e-learning. This could lead on importance of aligning e-learning strategies with existing instructional methods to maximize their impact.

Both teachers and students recognize the importance of best practices in e-learning integration, such as adding interactive and multimedia components and updating e-learning materials on a regular basis. Their dedication to these methods raises the standard of TLE's e-learning experiences overall.

The significant relationship of perceived attitudes towards challenges faced in e-learning integration suggests that fostering a more positive outlook can help overcome existing barriers. Encouraging a growth mindset and providing adequate training can facilitate a smoother transition to digital learning.

To address these challenges, project **TAMBAGE** has been proposed to improve attitudes of learners toward e-learning to ensure a more effective and sustainable e-learning integration in TLE.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following recommendations were drawn:

The Department of Education may prioritize professional development programs that aligned to the needs of the teachers that specifically address challenges, focusing implementation for e-learning learning experiences.

School heads play a important role in promoting supportive environments where teachers feel empowered to address challenges openly, and they may encourage a culture of continuous improvement and experimentation in teaching methods.

Teachers are encouraged to actively engage in professional development opportunities, collaborate with peers, and advocate for necessary e-learning resources to enhance instructional effectiveness.

Students are encouraged to provide constructive feedback to teachers and actively participate in the e-learning process, embracing the opportunities presented by remote assignments.

Parents are encouraged to support the activity of the school related to e-learning activities as they may guide and assist their children with e-learning capabilities.

Future researchers should consider exploring localized challenges encountered by teachers and conduct longitudinal studies to deepen our understanding of the teacher's curriculum adaptation to e-learning over time. This holistic approach, encompassing professional development, resource allocation, and supportive environments, can contribute to a more effective and adaptive educational system. Future studies may be done to focus on similar research with different variables shall be undertaken by other researchers for the verification of the result of the present research considering other factors affecting pedagogical competence and widening the scope of the location of the study for the researchers to verify of the result of the present study.

Utilization of the project TAMBAGE (Transforming Accessible Methods and Bridging Achievements Guided E-learning) may encourage assessing the effectiveness and enhancing teachers' professional expertise both teachers and students. The study may commence with a baseline assessment to establish the current state of teacher skills, classroom practices, and the overall learning environment.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers of this study ensured full compliance with ethical standards in conducting this research. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents before their participation, and they were given the freedom to withdraw from the study at any time without any consequences. The anonymity of all respondents was strictly maintained, and their personal information was kept confidential in accordance with data privacy regulations. The well-being of the participants was safeguarded throughout the study, ensuring that no harm, discomfort, or undue pressure was exerted upon them. Furthermore, the researchers affirm that there were no conflicts of interest in the conduct of this study. Plagiarism was strictly avoided, and all sources were properly cited in

accordance with academic integrity guidelines. The interpretation of the findings was conducted without bias, ensuring objectivity and reliability. The results of this study are used solely for research purposes, contributing to the academic and practical discourse on integrating E-learning in teaching TLE subjects.

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REFERENCES

- Al-Adwan, A. S., Albelbisi, N. A., Hujran, O., Al-Rahmi, W. M., & Alkhalifah, A. (2021). Developing a holistic success model for sustainable e-learning: A structural equation modeling approach. *Sustainability*, 13(16), 9453.
- Ashish, L., & Anitha, G. (2024, August). Transforming Education: The Impact Of ICT And Data Mining On Student Outcomes. In 2024 7th International Conference on Circuit Power and Computing Technologies (ICCPCT) (Vol. 1, pp. 675-683). IEEE.
- Asino, T. I., & Pulay, A. (2019). Student perceptions on the role of the classroom environment on computer supported collaborative learning. *TechTrends*, 63(2), 179-187.
- Bangcasan, J. O. (2023). The Mediating Effect of Employee Motivation On the Relationship between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies (Doctoral dissertation, University of Mindanao).
- Bangcasan, J. O. (2023). The Mediating Effect of Employee Motivation On the Relationship between Professional Knowledge and Instructional Strategies (Doctoral dissertation, University of Mindanao).
- Bates, A. T. (2019). Teaching in a digital age: Guidelines for designing teaching and learning. Open Textbook Library.
- Benbunan-Fich, R. (2008). Blended learning in higher education: framework, principles, and guidelines.
- Curan, N.C. (2023). Factors Affecting Students' Interest in Learning Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Competencies in the Junior High Schools in Echague, Isabel. *Cosmos An International Journal of Art & Higher Education*, 2(2)
- Encarnacion, R. F. E., Galang, A. A. D., & Hallar, B. J. A. (2021). The impact and effectiveness of e-learning on teaching and learning. **Online Submission**, 5(1), 383-397.
- Ertmer, P. A., Ottenbreit-Leftwich, A. T., Sadik, O., Sendurur, E., & Sendurur, P. (2012). Teacher beliefs and technology integration practices: A critical relationship. *Computers & education*, 59(2), 423-435.
- Hauver, A. D. (2022). It Takes Brains: Cultivating the Learning Process for Effective Science Communication (Doctoral dissertation, The University of Nebraska-Lincoln).
- Jang, J., Ko, Y., Shin, W. S., & Han, I. (2021). Augmented reality and virtual reality for learning: An examination using an extended technology acceptance model. *IEEE access*, 9, 6798-6809.

- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for teacher knowledge. *Teachers college record*, 108(6), 1017-1054.
- Pizon, M. G., & Ytoc, S. T (2022). A Path Model to Infer Mathematics Performance: The Interrelated Impact of Motivation, Attitude, Learning Style and Teaching Strategies Variables. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(3), 315-330.
- Radtke, J. (2023). E-Participation in Post-Pandemic-Times: A Silver Bullet for Democracy in the Twenty-First Century?. Potsdam: Research Institute for Sustainability.
- Rajaram, K. (2023). Future of learning: Teaching and learning strategies. In *Learning Intelligence: Innovative and Digital Transformative Learning Strategies: Cultural and Social Engineering Perspectives* (pp. 3-53). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
- Rodriguez, C. F., & Habla, F. A (2023). Learning Continuity in Technology and Livelihood Education (TLE) Instruction Through Information and Communication Technology (ICT) Integration.
- Scherer, R., Siddiq, F., & Tondeur, J. (2019). The technology acceptance model (TAM): A meta-analytic structural equation modeling approach to explaining teachers' adoption of digital technology in education. *Computers & education*, 128, 13-35.
- Seufert, S., Guggemos, J., & Sailer, M. (2021). Technology-related knowledge, skills, and attitudes of pre-and in-service teachers: The current situation and emerging trends. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 115, 106552.
- Simanjuntak, M. B., Suseno, M., Setiadi, S., Lustyantje, N., & Barus, I. R. G. R. G. (2022). Integration of curricula (curriculum 2013 and cambridge curriculum for junior high school level in three subjects) in pandemic situation. *Ideas: Jurnal Pendidikan, Sosial, dan Budaya*, 8(1), 77-86.
- Teo, T. (2011). Factors influencing teachers' intention to use technology: Model development and test. *Computers & Education*, 57(4), 2432-2440.
- Ware, H. B. (2006). *Learner-centered e-learning: An exploration of learner-centered practices in online and traditional instruction in higher education*. Louisiana State University and Agricultural & Mechanical College.
- Yu, T., Dai, J., & Wang, C. (2023). Adoption of blended learning: Chinese university students' perspectives. *Humanities and Social Sciences Communications*, 10(1), 1-16.